

Mercury seen from Mars (local Extrema of apparent brightness from 2000-2007)

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round the Mars.

Explanation: mag = stellar magnitude, °=degree, '= angular minute, " = angular second

AE= astronomical unit =149598500 km

Date	apparent Brightness [mag]	Phase in per cent	Distance of Mercury from Mars [AE]	Angle-distance to Sun [°]	apparent Dia-meter ["]	Distance of Mercury to Sun [AE]
6.2.2000	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.09	0.69-0.71 decreasing	6.1	0.32-0.33 decreasing
26.2.-28.2.2000	-0.47	73-81 increasing	1.56-1.63 increasing	11.12-11.97 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.35 increasing
31.3.-6.4.2000	+0.16	92-97 increasing	1.86-1.91 decreasing	6.39-9.16 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
19.4.-21.4.2000	+0.07	71-75 decreasing	1.63-1.67 decreasing	13.83-14.12 increasing	4.0-4.1 increasing	0.40-0.42 decreasing
13.5.2000	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.23	0.60	5.4	0.31
3.6.-5.6.2000	+0.12	68-75 increasing	1.66-1.72 increasing	13.15-13.59 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.39-0.41 increasing
22.6.-27.6.2000	+0.27	95-99 increasing	1.99-2.04 increasing	4.13-6.68 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
25.7.-27.7.2000	-0.16	75-82 decreasing	1.76-1.83 decreasing	10.04-10.81 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.35-0.37 decreasing
16.8.-17.8.2000	weaker than +6.00	<1	1.32	1.21-1.22 increasing	5.1	0.32
26.10.-28.10.2000	-0.40	83-90 decreasing	1.86-1.92 decreasing	7.17-8.33 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.34 decreasing
21.11.2000	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.29-1.30 decreasing	1.30-1.31 increasing	5.1-5.2 increasing	0.37
26.1.-29.1.2001	-0.65	91-97 decreasing	1.87-1.93 decreasing	4.28-6.10 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
1.3.2001	weaker than +9.00	<1	1.17	0.61-0.62 increasing	5.7	0.43
29.4.2001	-0.89	99-100 decreasing	1.83-1.84 decreasing	1.71-1.99 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.31
15.6.-16.6.2001	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.00	1.41-1.42 decreasing	6.7	0.47
29.7.-30.7.2001	-1.00	97-100 increasing	1.70-1.73 increasing	2.24-4.06 decreasing	3.9	0.30-0.32 increasing
3.10.2001	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.98-0.99 increasing	2.00-2.02 decreasing	6.8	0.39-0.40 decreasing
28.10.-31.10.2001	-0.84	84-91 increasing	1.58-1.64 increasing	7.94-9.60 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
12.1.2002	weaker	<1	1.11	0.39-0.40	6.0	0.32

	than +8.00			decreasing		
31.1.-2.2. 2002	-0.36	71-79 increasing	1.57-1.64 increasing	11.60-12.34 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.34-0.36 increasing
4.3.-10.3 2002	+0.17	96-99 decreasing	1.92-1.96 decreasing	3.80-6.63 increasing	3.4-3.5 increasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
26.3.-29.3. 2002	+0.03	69-78 decreasing	1.64-1.72 decreasing	12.86-13.49 increasing	3.9-4.1 increasing	0.38-0.41 decreasing
18.4.2002	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.25	0.77	5.3	0.31
9.5.-14.5. 2002	+0.23	66-78 increasing	1.66-1.79 increasing	13.00-13.93 decreasing	3.7-4.0 decreasing	0.40-0.43 increasing
27.5.-29.5 2002	+0.31	93-95 increasing	1.99-2.01 increasing	7.29-8.04 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
29.6.-3.7. 2002	-0.20	75-85 decreasing	1.78-1.87 decreasing	9.22-10.43 increasing	3.6-3.8 increasing	0.34-0.37 decreasing
23.7.2002	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.32	1.27-1.28 increasing	5.1	0.32-0.33 increasing
1.10.-3.10. 2002	-0.45	86-90 decreasing	1.88-1.92 decreasing	6.93-7.68 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.32-0.33 decreasing
27.10.2002	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.28-1.29 decreasing	1.25-1.26 increasing	5.2	0.37-0.38 increasing
1.1.-3.1. 2003	-0.70	93-97 decreasing	1.87-1.91 decreasing	3.93-5.37 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
5.2.2003	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.13-1.14 decreasing	0.32-0.33 increasing	5.9	0.44
2.4.-4.4. 2003	-0.92	99-100 decreasing	1.80-1.82 decreasing	0.28-2.13 increasing	3.7	0.31
24.5.-25.5. 2003	weaker than +7.50	<1	0.98	1.79-1.80 decreasing	6.8	0.46
3.7.-5.7. 2003	-0.99	94-99 increasing	1.67-1.71 increasing	2.90-5.62 decreasing	3.9-4.0 decreasing	0.30-0.32 increasing
9.9.-10.9. 2003	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.00-1.01 increasing	1.75-1.76 decreasing	6.6-6.7 decreasing	0.37-0.38 decreasing
3.10.-6.10. 2003	-0.77	81-89 increasing	1.56-1.63 increasing	8.79-10.38 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.31-0.33 increasing
18.12.2003	weaker than +7.50	<1	1.14	0.11	5.9	0.32
7.1.-8.1. 2004	-0.25	71-76 increasing	1.60-1.64 increasing	12.23-12.56 decreasing	4.1-4.2 decreasing	0.35-0.37 increasing
4.2.-12.2. 2004	+0.18	98-100 decreasing	1.96-1.99 decreasing	0.80-4.70 increasing	3.4	0.46-0.47 decreasing
29.2.-4.3. 2004	-0.01	69-80 decreasing	1.65-1.76 decreasing	11.94-12.86 increasing	3.8-4.1 increasing	0.37-0.40 decreasing
23.3.2004	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.27	0.90-0.91 increasing	5.3	0.31
16.4.-20.4. 2004	+0.32	69-78 increasing	1.71-1.82 increasing	13.14-14.05 decreasing	3.7-3.9 decreasing	0.42-0.44 increasing
27.4.-1.5. 2004	+0.35	87-92 increasing	1.93-1.99 increasing	9.11-10.84 decreasing	3.4-3.5 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing
4.6.-6.6. 2004	-0.25	78-85 decreasing	1.81-1.87 decreasing	8.88-9.80 increasing	3.6-3.7 increasing	0.34-0.36 decreasing
27.6.2004	weaker	<1	1.32-1.33	1.31-1.32	5.0-5.1	0.33-0.34

	than +7.00		decreasing	increasing	increasing	increasing
4.9.-7.9. 2004	-0.49	85-93 decreasing	1.87-1.94 decreasing	5.83-7.73 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
2.10.2004	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.26	1.16-1.17 increasing	5.3	0.39
6.12.-7.12. 2004	-0.75	96-97 decreasing	1.87-1.89 decreasing	3.81-4.36 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.32 decreasing
12.1.2005	weaker than +10.50	<1	1.10	0.02	6.1	0.45
7.3.-9.3. 2005	-0.95	99-100 decreasing	1.78-1.80 decreasing	0.93-1.37 increasing	3.7-3.8 increasing	0.31
1.5.-2.5. 2005	weaker than +7.00	<1	0.97	2.07-2.09 decreasing	6.9	0.45-0.46 decreasing
7.6.-8.6. 2005	-0.98	93-97 increasing	1.65-1.69 increasing	4.65-6.19 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
16.8.2005	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.02-1.03 increasing	1.44-1.45 decreasing	6.5-6.6 decreasing	0.36-0.37 decreasing
7.9.-9.9. 2005	-0.69	78-86 increasing	1.56-1.62 increasing	9.67-10.92 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.32-0.34 increasing
23.11.2005	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.17	0.14	5.7	0.31
12.12.-15.12. 2005	-0.13	68-77 increasing	1.60-1.68 increasing	12.36-13.02 decreasing	4.0-4.2 decreasing	0.36-0.39 increasing
7.1.-14.1. 2006	+0.20	99-100 decreasing	2.00-2.01 increasing	2.00-2.23 increasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 decreasing
4.2.-7.2. 2006	-0.06	72-79 decreasing	1.70-1.77 decreasing	11.47-12.12 increasing	3.8-4.0 increasing	0.36-0.39 decreasing
27.2.2006	weaker than +6.50	<1	1.29	1.02-1.03 increasing	5.2	0.31-0.32 increasing
10.5.-11.5. 2006	-0.30	82-84 decreasing	1.85-1.87 decreasing	8.72-9.01 increasing	3.6	0.33-0.35 decreasing
2.6.2006	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.32-1.33 decreasing	1.33-1.34 increasing	5.0-5.1 increasing	0.34-0.35 increasing
10.8.-12.8. 2006	-0.54	87-94 decreasing	1.88-1.94 decreasing	5.42-7.20 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.31-0.33 decreasing
8.9.2006	weaker than +8.50	<1	1.23-1.24 decreasing	1.04-1.05 increasing	5.4	0.40-0.41 increasing
10.11.-12.11. 2006	-0.79	95-99 decreasing	1.85-1.89 decreasing	2.38-4.47 increasing	3.5-3.6 increasing	0.30-0.32 decreasing
21.12.2006	weaker than +10.00	<1	1.06-1.07 decreasing	0.41-0.42 increasing	6.2-6.3 increasing	0.46
9.2.-12.2. 2007	-0.97	99-100 increasing	1.76-1.77 increasing	0.93-2.19 decreasing	3.8	0.30-0.31 increasing
9.4.-10.4. 2007	weaker than +6.50	<1	0.96-0.97 increasing	2.21-2.23 decreasing	6.9	0.43-0.44 decreasing
12.5.-14.5. 2007	-0.95	90-96 increasing	1.62-1.67 increasing	5.60-7.48 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.31-0.32 increasing
23.7.2007	weaker than +7.00	<1	1.05	1.10-1.11 decreasing	6.4	0.34-0.35 decreasing
13.8.-15.8. 2007	-0.60	77-83 increasing	1.56-1.62 increasing	10.53-11.32 decreasing	4.1-4.3 decreasing	0.33-0.34 increasing
21.9.-24.9	+0.16	88-92	1.77-1.82	10.37-11.80	3.7-3.8	0.46-0.47

2007		decreasing	decreasing	increasing	increasing	decreasing
1.10.-7.10. 2007	+0.13	67-80 decreasing	1.56-1.69 decreasing	14.04-15.27 increasing	4.0-4.3 increasing	0.41-0.45 decreasing
29.10.2007	weaker than +8.00	<1	1.20	0.37	5.6	0.31
18.11.-20.11. 2007	-0.02	69-74 increasing	1.63-1.68 increasing	12.90-13.20 decreasing	4.0-4.1 decreasing	0.37-0.39 increasing
11.12.-17.12. 2007	+0.23	98-100 increasing	2.00-2.04 increasing	1.21-3.95 decreasing	3.3-3.4 decreasing	0.46-0.47 increasing

Made with STELLARIUM and PLANETARIUM.